

Collective Security

Artur Vivtoria

National power can be strengthened with the support of another state or group of countries to increase the deterrent capacity that the combination of standard or mutual interests ruling out possible aggression.

Collective Security is effective only when three primary conditions are met:

- The Collective Security system should be able to deploy a force sufficiently capable of taking advantage over a potential offender or coalition of offenders to discourage any attack;
- Nations that are part of the Collective Security system must have the same conception of Security and be willing to defend it; and
- These nations must be prone to reevaluate their conflicting political interests in the name of the collective benefit to put in place the necessary defensive measures.

1. Basics of Planning

1.1 Concept Planning is the submission of a Plan to a set of activities (classic concept).

Defining Planning is a previously ordered set of actions aimed at achieving established objectives, including the allocation of human, material, and financial resources, as well as evaluation procedures. In the field of government planning, a distinction must be made between Planning and Planning. The first term refers to state control of the total factors of the economy using a Plan: it is Imposition Planning. In contrast, Planning means the subordination of economic factors to a pre-established plan by the Government: and the so-called Indicative Planning.

Actually, in the vast majority of countries, government action takes place through indicative Planning, monetary, fiscal, exchange rate, wage, and other policies.

1.2 Planning Phases

Planning is also an interactive process that unfolds into different phases. These phases necessarily have the same meaning as those identified in the composition of the decision-making process:

Diagnosis, what is sought is knowledge of reality in all its aspects and its probable evolution (projections of the future).

The formulation of the Policy establishes the purpose and objectives of planning (desired future).

Objectives define what is intended to be achieved within a given planning horizon (period of a plan, program, or project).

Programming consists of detailing all the set of means necessary to achieve the objectives. They unfold into plans, programs, projects, and activities, identifying the resources needed for their implementation. Implementation defines and prepares the sectors responsible for the various programs, projects, and events.

In Control, the physical and financial monitoring mechanisms of the execution are established. In all phases of Planning, information is the most relevant tool available to the planner (information about the reality in which it is intended to act and its evolution).

1.3 Planning Process

The planning process involves the specification of objectives, the selection of means and instruments, and the use of these means and tools. In other words: define goals, resources are sought and applied.

Modern Planning Techniques mainly aim at:

- Build probable images of the future based on real analysis and its likely evolution;
- Formulate the vision
- Objective to be achieved (desired future);
- Identify the means to achieve the goals; and
- Design and drive enforcement mechanisms.

2. STRATEGIC PLANNING

Strategic Planning is the process of formulating strategies to seize opportunities and counteract environmental threats by leveraging the strengths and eliminating the weaknesses of the organization to achieve its Mission.

Strengths are internal and controllable variables that provide a favourable condition for the organization concerning its environment;

Weaknesses are internal and manageable variables that cause an unfavourable situation for the organization concerning its environment;

Opportunities are external variables that are not controllable by the organization, which can create favourable conditions for the organization, as long as it has requirements with interest to enjoy them;

Threats are external variables that are not controllable by the organization, which can create unfavourable conditions for the organization; and

The mission is the determination of the central motive of strategic Planning, that is, the determination of where the organization wants to go.

It corresponds to a horizon within which the organization acts or may act. Therefore the Mission represents the *raison d'être* of the organization.

The definition of the Mission should guide the analysis of the external and internal environments of the organization.

From the relationship between environment analysis and Mission, we extract the summaries for the elaboration of the planning stages.

Strategic Planning deals with the organization as a whole and with its environment (systemic view). In short, Strategic Planning should seek (know) and make better use of the Strong Bridges by eliminating or adapting their Weaknesses, identifying and taking advantage of external Opportunities, removing or reducing the negative impact of Threats.

3. PROSPECTIVE TECHNIQUES

3.1 Prospective is a multidisciplinary approach that seeks to explore the possible assumptions of future events in the medium and long term.

Examine the policies and strategies that can be adopted to bend the course of evolution of the reality that will affect the desired future targets and undesirable events.

Foresight stems desire to move from a passive attitude towards the future to an active position.

The planning process is based on the construction of Scenarios.

The Scenario is the description of a possible future with the explanation of the events that would lead to its realization. This vision of the future uses different techniques for the construction of Scenarios.

- Prediction;
- Classic Prediction; and
- Prospective (the study of the future).

Prediction belongs to the group of qualitative techniques and is therefore based on intuitions, guesses, opinions, etc.

Predict and announce the anticipated occurrence of a given event, without any discussion, as it considers it a probabilistically specific event.

The present was determined by the past, and the present will determine the future. Thus, projecting past events allows us to visualize a single future. The most commonly used techniques in Classic Prediction are:

- Extrapolation: Variables that have evolved in a certain way from the past to the present will continue to evolve equally in the present to the future;
- Analogy: Identification of a current case with an already occurred one. It is assumed that the result of the current situation will be the same as the one that occurred;
- Causality: persistence of a cause; and
- Correlations found between certain events, even if the reason cannot be discovered.

Foresight means seeing ahead, far away, or all that concerns the future. In other words, it is having a "prospective view."

3.2 Scenarios

Prospective is the view of all variables of a situation to visualize what impacts they will have on each other and what impact they will have together.

Prospective methods start from structural assumptions that are based on the past but are open to change at all times.

These structural assumptions refer to events and facts that signal that their evolution will influence the shaping of Possible Future Scenarios.

The analysis of these developments by the Strategic Decision Makers will lead to actions that modify the present to reorient the course of events towards the desired future.

Prospective Scenario is the set formed by the coherent description of the evolution of events from one current situation to another future.

This trajectory may occur facts of a significant nature that lead to a change in the desired path. It is the so-called Future Facts that generate Future Events.

Future Fact is a fact that has occurred or occurring, that can significantly affect the evolution of the current state of the actual situation. Also can be a factor of change that will produce a significant trend tomorrow.

This evolution is called the Future Event, which is, in short, a coherent and plausible hypothesis for a future event. In the face of Future Events, Strategic Decision Makers are forced to take actions that bring the Scenario back to the desired or nearest path possible to the desired one.

3.3 Scenario Building

The Prospective Method in Scenario Building involves three distinct phases:

- Exploration of Possible Futures: early stage. Reflection is free (whatever the imagination allows);
- Delimitation of Plausible Futures: intermediate step. All that is possible, subject to some limiting factors (time, resource availability, obstacles, ethical assumptions); and
- Choice of Desirable Futures: final phase.

This process results in two types of scenarios:

- Exploratory Scenario is the description of a future situation, based on plausible, coherent, and intelligible assumptions.
- Desired Scenario which is a Scenario derived from an Exploratory Scenario, taking into consideration the will of a community, reflecting its aspirations and expectations and outlining what is expected to be achieved.

When designing a particular scenario, one must not forget its so-called primary attributes:

- Relevance: should be related to the theme under study;
- Internal Consistency: events of the same Scenario cannot be conflicting;
- Plausibility: feasible circumstances of occurrence; and

- Intelligibility: easy to understand.

It can then be concluded that the role of the Scenario is to organize uncertainty into a limited number of options to enable decisions despite the high degree of uncertainty involved.

4. STRATEGIC PLANNING METHOD

4.1 Introduction

The Method is an orderly set of procedures for obtaining specific results. It uses logical processes that lead to knowledge and action. It is also an interactive process characterized by a sequence of operations in which the object of each of them is the fundamental element of the immediately following one.

Planning is a process of optimizing decisions, that is, of choices. It needs a knowledge of the reality in which these decisions operate, in particular, the conditions of their factuality. It is aware of the present and future-oriented, living, to a greater or lesser extent, with the risk and uncertainty inherent in Planning.

The planning method presented here aims at streamlining the macro decisions of a government, with emphasis on the design of defense actions. It exercises political rationality, that is, the choice of Objectives, based on the identification of social values, needs, interests and aspirations, synthesized by the Common Good, following the principles that guide the Doctrinal Elements, which gives it its characteristic.

The Method, on the other hand, is nothing more and, being, the rational systematization of the decision-making process that, under the inspiration of those same principles, seeks to ground, guide and justify the strategic action. It is the product of technical rationality, applied to strategic action, allowing the examination of the feasibility of objectives within a given time horizon. As a continuous and permanent activity, it is not just about making plans, which are just one of its steps. On the contrary, it encompasses a whole complex set of procedures necessary for decision-making and its execution, which can be described as follows:

- Knowledge of the political, economic, psychosocial, military and scientific-technological reality, both internally and externally;
- Examination, interpretation and prospective analysis of the environment;
- Identification of basic needs and obstacles that hinder or may preclude meeting those needs;
- Identification of crises as conditions for the establishment of the Government Objectives;

- Evaluation of the legitimacy, timeliness, and convenience of events based on the basic premises of an ethical nature raised;
- Survey of the capacity of current, potential and future power;
- Survey of existing policies and strategies;
- Preparation of prospective scenarios that will condition the planned actions;
- Analysis of the sequences of strategic actions (trajectories) and the choice of the most suitable for achieving the Goals;
- Preparation of government plans, programs and projects, in line with the previously formulated strategic guidelines; and
- Execution of planned actions and their monitoring, evaluation, and Control.

The Method presupposes in its formulation and execution the active and creative involvement of the whole society. The planned actions are, therefore, enforceable only when they are the responsibility of the Government.

4.2 Basis of the Method

The Planning Method, presented here, is based on two fundamental pillars:

The Theoretical Planning Bases, common to any planning method which gives it its characteristic by turning to objectives;

Participatory, for involving society in the formulation and execution of Planning.

4.3 Method Phases

The planning phases are related to the three primary phases of the decision-making process:

A - Diagnosis phase (analysis);

B - Political stage (choice); and

C - Strategic Phase (action).

4.4 - Diagnosis Phase

This Planning phase has two necessary steps: Environment analysis; The raising of power. In the Diagnosis or Analysis Phase, we first seek to examine the external and internal environments.

External environment analysis involves identifying threats and opportunities that may positively (opportunities) or negatively (threats) interfere with the performance of the

Government system. On the other hand, the internal environment analysis seeks to know the strengths and weaknesses of the Government system and its interaction with the identified threats and opportunities, as well as to evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of existing plans, programs and projects. In National Security, in international relations, it is essential to identify strategic areas of importance to national interests.

It is essential to identify the current or potential crises, examining in each case, their origins, and repercussions.

Then, the second stage of this phase: the lifting of power. Now it is intended to raise the needs, thus understood as needs that must be met.

The study must be prospective, as some of them, which are of little relevance at present, may become imperative in the future.

The needs study must be prospective, as some of them, which are of little relevance at present, may become imperative in the future. The final result of the Diagnosis should contain initial data and preliminary conclusions that will be used throughout the process. It should relate the underlying assumptions of an ethical nature necessary to the political decision and the elements that facilitate the strategic decision.

4.5 Political Phase

The ultimate purpose of this phase is the definition of objectives or the establishment of policy guidelines (what to do?)

Aimed at guiding the various governmental sectors. It is a step of choice that provides guidance and parameters for decision making.

It means studying how the Government will look in the future, in the face of opportunities and threats, strengths and weaknesses, and underlying assumptions that are exhaustively considered at the diagnostic stage.

At this stage, specific targets may also be set as a means of monitoring the implementation process of what is planned.

The Planning Method recommends the use of specific decision-making tools (decision trees, scenarios, images of the future).

Planners use scenario building as a way of envisioning the future, albeit uncertain. The scenario-building technique begins by identifying Future Provoking Facts.

Facts that have already occurred or are occurring that may have an impact on the topic under study are identified from studies carried out at the diagnosis stage.

Starting from the identified, we obtain the so-called Future Events that are coherent and plausible hypotheses for a possible future event.

The obtaining of Future Events, based on the Future Provoquing Facts, is done in two stages.

First, a brainstorming session (in a phase of free creativity) is used to raise preliminary future events.

On these initial future events, conditions identified in the diagnostic step are applied, thus obtaining a set of activities called definitive future events.

The definitive future events composing the Exploratory Scenarios are a consistent set of future events.

Exploratory scenarios are, therefore, extremely useful tools for decision making.

There are two techniques used for the elaboration of Exploratory Scenarios:

- Elaboration of three exploratory scenarios: Optimistic, pessimistic, and medium.

This elaboration is made from the examination of the definitive future events through content analysis; and

- Elaboration of exploratory scenarios, using Delphi and Cross Impact techniques, in addition to a specific computer program.

The detailed study of the mentioned techniques and the presentation of the computer program will be conducted throughout the study of the Method.

Whatever technique is employed, the next step will be to determine the Most Likely Scenario.

The most likely Scenario will be established from the selection of definitive future events from the three exploratory scenarios prepared (optimistic, pessimistic, and medium).

Following the elaboration of the most probable Scenario, it is submitted to the Strategic Decision Maker with all the information and conclusions already collected will elaborate on the Desired or Normative Scenario.

This last Scenario is defined by "objectives to be achieved," which are nothing more than the Goals of Government.

The choice of the desired Scenario and therefore, the highest level decision in the entire planning process.

4.6 - Strategic Phase

From this point, no longer is discussed the objectives of Planning, but rather the use of the means to achieve them. This phase has four quite distinct steps: strategic design, programming, execution, and Control.

The strategic conception stage comprises the study, definition, and indication of the strategies to be followed.

It starts by defining strategic actions imagined achieving the Goals, using its tools (such as the Brainstorming technique).

It should be considered that usually, the intended objectives are only made with a sequence of strategic actions.

This sequence of strategic actions is called the trajectory. In this case, another trajectory (the composition of the trajectories initially considered) should be elaborated.

At the strategic design stage, the trajectory must be submitted to the test (suitability, feasibility, and acceptability).

The suitability test should answer the following question: Does the trajectory guarantee that the desired objective is achieved within the required time frame?

If the answer is negative, the trajectory should be dismissed as inappropriate.

If the answer is positive, the trajectory is submitted to the feasibility test, raising the following question: with the available means and possible to implement the intended actions? Again, negative response means discarding the trajectory under study, now as unenforceable.

The first two tests are "yes or no," not allowing graduation. The third and last test is the acceptability test and allows grading: considering all known data, does the cost/benefit of the intended trajectory justify its implementation?

On the other hand, if there are several trajectories (all suitable and executable) ensuring the achievement of the same objective, which one has the best cost/benefit ratio?

Thus comes the Choice of Strategic Option, set of trajectories that ensure the achievement of the desired Scenario. The next step of the Strategic Phase is the programming that seeks operability between the chosen paths.

From the Strategic Choice, strategic guidelines are established that seek to guide the actions of the various sectors involved. These are government strategic planning at the national level, and when linked to the process, these guidelines can be broken down into sectoral, regional, and specific guidelines.

When focused on Security, through specific Defense actions, they should understand Internal and External Defense Actions.

There is a close relationship between the resulting Strategic Guidelines in the fields of Development and National Security.

The programming stage ends with the preparation of Plans that, seeking the indispensable operation of what was planned, must be prepared according to the political decision within the strategic option and respecting the guidelines contained in the strategic guidelines.

These Plans shall present programs, projects, and activities that specify objectives, set goals, resources (budgets), executing entities, as well as the mechanisms for their monitoring, evaluation, and Control. It should be noted, for example, that Strategic Actions find their financial counterpart in budgets and, therefore, must be subordinated to them.

National Defense Planning should involve the hostile universe, without neglecting the adverse factors with the potential to generate antagonisms.

The study of Political-Strategic Crisis and Armed Conflict Hypotheses is relevant, where the corresponding strategic actions mainly concern External Defense Actions.

On the other hand, preventive and / or operative actions concerning Law and Order Guarantee should be in line with specific actions related to Public Safety.

At the implementation stage, Planning is achieved through an orderly process of transformation that aims to move from the current situation to the desired situation by implementing the actions.

The coordination (management) of the execution of Planning focuses on its rationalization, with a view to efficiency, effectiveness, and effectiveness of the use of means (Power), that is, to its best performance.

The management function is of fundamental importance, and it is responsible for solving the resulting pauses, including the introduction of necessary changes in the organizational structures.

Bibliography

Claude, I L Swords Into Plowshares: The Problems and Progress of International Organization, volume 4 Posted: 1971

Jr Claude, I L, Collective Security Europe and Asia Posted: 1992

P G Danchin Things Fall Apart: The Concept of Collective Security in International Law

United Nations Reform and the New Collective Security Posted: 2009

J Delbruck Collective Security Encyclopaedia of Public International Law Posted: 1992

H C Johnson, G Niemeyer Collective Security: The Validity of an Ideal International Organization, volume 8 Posted: 1954

M Koskeniemi From Apology to Utopia: The Structure of International Legal Argument Posted: 2005

J J Mearscheimer The Promise of International Institutions International Security, volume 19, issue 3, p. 5 – 49 Posted: 1994